

IMPORTANCE OF MEDIA COMPETENCY IN THE STUDY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *This article explores the role and importance of media competence in improving the quality of education in elementary schools. It also recommended the shortcomings and problems that we currently facing and necessary actions to be taken.*

Keywords: Media, components, tendency, textbook, interactivity, didactic study, primary school, lesson process, animation

Annotatsiya: *Maqola Ingliz tili darslari samaradorligini oshirishda mediyakompetentlikni rivojlantirishga bag‘ishlanadi. Shuningdek electron darslik tuzulishi , ulardan samarali foydalanish usullariga alohida to‘xtalib o‘tiladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: Mediakompetentlik, boshlang‘ich sinflar, didaktik ta‘lim animatsiyalar, interfaol, component, raqamli, samara, dars jarayoni.

Аннотация: *Статья посвящена разработке системы использования медиакомпетенции для повышения эффективности уроков Английского языка. И также главное внимания предназначены разработке электронных учебников и способам их эффективного использования.*

Ключевые слова: Медиа, компетенция, электронных учебников, в эффективность дидактика, интерактивный.

Introduction

The inclusion of younger schoolchildren in the learning process requires a conscious choice by the child of the necessary means of searching for educational information to solve the problems posed, its analysis and evaluation, generalization and appropriate decision-making. At the same time, the student constantly turns to ICT tools and multimedia technologies when solving educational tasks. Thus, the degree of development of students' information competence determines the effectiveness of mastering the educational program of primary school, and also contributes to the development of a person's readiness to adapt to a changing digital educational environment.

At the same time, under the information competence of younger schoolchildren, we understand the ability and ability to independently search, analyze, select, process and transmit the necessary information in order to solve the tasks set. In this regard, it is necessary to search for modern means that contribute to the effective organization of the

educational process in primary schools, aimed at the formation of information. In our opinion, the didactic capabilities of multimedia technologies make it possible to solve the task effectively, and their implementation requires a revision of the methodology for building the educational process in primary school.

Methods

Modern multimedia technologies have great opportunities in the search, visualization and structuring of information and have a direct impact on the motivation of students, the speed of perception of the material, fatigue and, thus, on the effectiveness of the educational process as a whole. However, their use in the framework of lessons has limited time, resource, and subject possibilities. Whereas in extracurricular activities, these restrictions are lifted. It is the integration of multimedia technologies into the already established forms and methods of organizing extracurricular activities in primary schools that will create effective conditions for the formation of students' information competence. In this regard, the purpose of this study is to find opportunities for the use of multimedia technologies in extracurricular activities as a means of forming the information competence of younger schoolchildren. Review of domestic and foreign literature on the research topic For this study, the work of foreign and domestic scientists is especially important and significant, aimed at considering the essential characteristics of an information-competent person as having the skills to work with various sources of information, computers and multimedia technologies. A number of studies by both domestic and foreign authors are devoted to the consideration of the terms "competence" and "information competence". In the understanding of the German researcher in the field of education E. Klima, the concept of personality predisposition is considered from the perspective of the compatibility of three components: it is teachable, contextualized, and cognitive. With regard to the characteristics of learning ability, it is recognized that every person who does not have competence can, in principle, learn this [5].

Results

In the works of M. Eraut, competence is understood as the ability of a person to perform tasks and roles through actions in accordance with expected results [6]. The general concept of defining the term "competence" is defined in M. Mulder's research as an integrated set of abilities that arises from clusters of knowledge, skills and relationships. Technical and technological Use of applications to choose from: Microsoft PowerPoint, Google Slides, Prezi, Canva, Apple Keynote. Mockingbird is an online tool for creating various parts of a project. Evaluative-reflective Acquaintance and use of the Cacao Internet service (allows you to create diagrams on the Internet) Communicative Acquaintance and use of the Lumzy Internet service. With this service, you can create charts and share them with classmates. The inclusion of multimedia technologies in the process of extracurricular activities, aimed at creating complex conditions for the formation of all components of information competence. Working within the framework

of the modular course allowed students, without interrupting the solution of specific tasks, within each lesson, to get acquainted with the features and capabilities of the presented multimedia technologies and find their application in the development of their own projects.

Conclusion

Solving the problem of forming the media competence of future primary school teachers based on the deep understanding of modern pedagogical technologies is of great practical importance. The peculiarities of media education as a necessary component for the formation of media competence of future primary school teachers are considered. Finding out the relationship between theoretical and practical components in the method of forming the media competence of future primary school teachers is not accidental. The methodology, based on theoretical principles, sets requirements for management, which teachers should choose from the methodological arsenal for the practical implementation of cognitive activities of primary school children and achieve the educational goal of learning.

References

1. Alona Pluhina “ Methods of Forming Media Competence of Future Primary School Teachers” *Traektoriâ Nauki = Path of Science*. 2020. Vol. 6. No 9
2. Zhilavskaya, I. V. (2009). *Mediaobrazovanie molodezhnoj auditorii* [Media education for youth audience]. Tomsk: TIIT (in Russian) [Жилавская, И. В. (2009). *Медиаобразование молодежной аудитории*. Томск: ТИИТ]
3. Borchers, J.O. (1999) "Electronic Books: Definition, Genres, Interaction Design Patterns". Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, CHI99 Workshop: Designing Electronic Books, Pittsburgh, May
4. Bostock, S. (1998) *Courseware Engineering - an overview of the courseware development process*. University of Keele
5. Sh.Valiyeva “Requirements for the structure, content and design of multimedia electronic textbooks” *Theoretical & Applied Science Philadelphia, USA* issue 04, volume 96 published April 30, 2021